

POWER ENHANCEMENT BY ADOPTING ACTIVE POWER FILTER SCHEME WITH FUZZY LOGIC CONTROL UNDER GRID DISTORTIONS

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Abstract—Distribution line consists of a range of loads which are both linear and nonlinear, due to these nonlinear loads a harmonic current is developed at the source current which leads to detrimental disturbances, aging effect, poor power factor, and lower efficiency. Using active power filter is one of the viable solutions to eliminate power line harmonic currents generated by nonlinear loads and to improve the power factor. APF is operated in dual boost converter mode with constant switching frequency by using one cycle control method. The advantages of going for this type of control are it requires source current only and voltage as reference. And flip flops are used to generate the pulse signal to the converter which is connected in parallel with the distribution system. The inverter will provide phase shifting current. This phase shifted current is helpful in injecting and cancelling out the harmonic current and to achieve three phase unit power factor for the current to and from the powergrid. A DC capacitor is intended which acts as a source to the converter. In order to reduce the error and to produce firing signal, fuzzy logic based one cycle controller is used.

Index Terms—Nonlinear loads, Active Power Filter (APF), Dual -Boost converter, One-Cycle control, fuzzy logic controller.

INTRODUCTION

When a three phase supply is connected to a non linear load usually current harmonics are introduced. These current harmonics result in various problems such as Low efficiency, Power system voltage fluctuations, Low power factor. One of the viable solution to eliminate harmonics are power factor correction techniques such as passive power filters and active power filters. Passive filters are easy to design simple structure and economical but passive filters have many disadvantages, such as Resonance, fixed compensation character, Large size, possible overload. To defeat the above disadvantages due to Passive Filters, Active Power Filters (APFs) have been proposed as a current-harmonic compensator. The Active Power Filter is connected in shunt with nonlinear load. This approach is based on the principle of injecting harmonic current into the ac system, of the same amplitude but of reverse phase to that of the load current harmonics. This will more result in unity power factor and sinusoidal line currents in the input power system. In this case, a minor portion of the energy is processed, which may result in overall higher power processing potential and overall higher

energy efficiency [1]. These types of approaches are applicable for low-power (less than 5kVA) to high-power applications (around 100kVA). A three-phase shunt APF is generally comprises of a three-phase bridge converter and control circuitry. Most of the earlier used control approaches require to sense the load current and calculate its harmonics and reactive components in order to produce the position for scheming the current of the bridge converter[2]. Those control methods require fast and accurate calculation; therefore, high-performance A/D converters and an high-speed digital microprocessors are required, which yields high cost, low stability and complexity. So here introducing a promising solution based on One-Cycle control.

Fig.1 Power stage of the three-phase APF

The one-cycle control system do not require any use of multipliers in the control loop and the need for calculating current reference. The control circuitry is simple and more reliable. In pulse width-modulation active power filter, all the switches are run with switching frequency; hence, the switching losses are relatively much and more than that of the vector based active power filters. In this reference, a three-phase parallel filter with six-switch bridge voltage-source converter is operated.